

Study of complexes of cadmium(II) and lead(II) with mixed ligand (thioglycolate-oxalate/tartarate) systems in aqueous-methanol media at the dropping mercury electrode

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Complexes of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} have been studied in mixed ligand (thioglycolate-oxalate/tartarate) systems in aqueous-methanol solvent mixture. Ionic strength was maintained with KNO₃ ($\mu = 0.1 M$) and Triton X-100 was used as maxima suppressor. It was shown that only one mixed ligand entity MA_iX_j was formed, where $i = 2$ and $j = 1$ with both the metals. A and X are thioglycolate and oxalate or tartarate respectively. The composition and stability constants of the mixed ligand complexes formed have been evaluated.

As a part of our investigation¹ on the polarographic study of mixed ligand complexes of sulphur containing organic compounds in combination with carboxylic acids with several heavy metal ions, the present study of mixed ligand (thioglycolate-oxalate/tartarate) systems with Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} in aqueous-methanol mixture has been carried out at the dropping mercury electrode. The composition and stability constants of the complexes formed have been evaluated using Souchay and Faucherre's method².

Results and discussion

The present investigation reveals that the reduction of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} has been influenced by the formation of mixed ligand complexes of the type (Cd A₂X)⁴⁻ and (Pb A₂X)⁴⁻ in both the thioglycolate-oxalate and thioglycolate-tartarate systems. Stability constants $\log KMA_iX_j$ were found to be 9.11 for Cd^{II} and 10.24 for Pb^{II} in thioglycolate-oxalate system (10% aqueous-methanol media) and 5.89 for Cd^{II} and 7.04 for Pb^{II} in thioglycolate-tartarate system (20% aqueous-methanol media) respectively.

The reduction of both the metal ions in each mixed ligand system was studied at 30°C by recording polarograms of two different sets within the pH range (5–6).

For both the systems a constant concentration of Cd(NO₃)₂ or Pb(NO₃)₂ [0.66 mM with thioglycolate-oxalate system and 1.0 mM with thioglycolate-tartarate system] + 0.001% Triton X-100 + KNO₃ ($\mu = 1.0 M$) + 10% or 20% v/v methanol with constant concentration of oxalate or tartarate (C_X) and varying concentration of thioglycolate (C_A) as given in Tables 1a, b, c and d was taken as first set.

Another set was similarly carried out with constant concentration of thioglycolate and varying concentration of oxalate or tartarate taking C_A values for C_X and C_X values for C_A and all other constituents remaining the same.

All the plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $-E_{d,e}$ yielded straight lines with slopes, which agree with the theoretical value corresponding to $n = 2$ for both the Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} systems. The mean values of the slopes for different systems are given in Table 1 (a, b, c and d), showing the reversibility of the reduction. Linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ passed through the origin, established the diffusion controlled nature in each case. The $E_{1/2}$ evaluated from the log plots of each of the above mentioned C-V curves and corresponding diffusion current values have been recorded (Tables 1a, b, c and d). The $E_{1/2}$ values of the metal ion in mixed ligand system were more negative than that of the free metal ion since the ion must be first liberated from the complex, this requires certain amount of energy. From the shift in the half wave potential of the complexed metal ion and the concentration of the complex forming agents, both the stability constants of the complex and its composition can be calculated.

Souchay and Faucherre² derived an equation where a metal ion complexes with two ligand species simultaneously in solution. If the complexing reaction of the following type is considered

With the restriction that a single mixed ligand entity MA_iX_j is formed, then the shift in the $E_{1/2}$ of the polarographic wave of the metal ion as a function of the concentration of added

reagents A and X is given by :

$$\Delta E_{1/2} = 2.303 RT/nF \log [D_{\text{free}}/D_{\text{comp}}]^{1/2} - 2.303 RT/nF \log KMA_iX_j - i2.303 RT/nF \log C_A - j2.303 RT/nF \log C_X \quad (2)$$

The ratio $D_{\text{free}}/D_{\text{comp}}$ was obtained from the values of the limiting current from the plots of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $\log C_A$ with C_X kept constant and $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $\log C_X$ with C_A kept constant, values for i and j can be obtained by interest method because on differentiation :

$$[\partial (\Delta E_{1/2})/\partial (\log C_A)] C_X = -i2.303 RT/nF \quad (3)$$

$$[\partial (\Delta E_{1/2})/\partial (\log C_X)] C_A = -j2.303 RT/nF \quad (4)$$

Plots of (i) $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $\log C_A$ (C_X kept constant), (ii) $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $\log C_X$ (C_A kept constant) yielded straight lines and thus establish the formation of a single mixed ligand entity MA_iX_j .

The co-ordination numbers i and j of ligands A and X were determined from these plots and their values are given in Tables (1a, b, c and d) for each mixed ligand system. Integral values of i and j were used in the calculation of the stability constants $\log KMA_iX_j$ using eq. (2).

Table 1a. Cd^{II}-thioglycolate + oxalate mixed ligand system

Conc. C_A (M)	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
C_X (M)	0.000	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.006	0.008
30°C i_d (μ A)	6.200	3.900	3.600	3.000	1.800	1.600	3.600	3.500	2.900	1.900
$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	0.585	0.593	0.609	0.622	0.634	0.639	0.609	0.618	0.631	0.632
KMA_iX_j	-	8.997	8.971	9.137	9.158	9.127	9.110	9.110	9.155	9.247

Mean slope of log plots = 0.029, coordination numbers $i = 1.995$ and $j = 1.078$.

Mean $KMA_iX_j = 9.112$, standard deviation = ± 0.085 .

Table 1b. Pb^{II}-thioglycolate + oxalate mixed ligand system

Conc. C_A (M)	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
C_X (M)	0.000	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.006
30°C i_d (μ A)	6.200	5.500	4.600	4.000	3.500	2.600	5.600	4.100	3.600	3.200
$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	0.400	0.455	0.466	0.478	0.448	0.479	0.473	0.477	0.485	0.486
KMA_iX_j	-	10.31	10.16	10.21	10.23	10.20	10.31	10.28	10.21	10.22

Mean slope of log plots = 0.030, coordination numbers $i = 1.870$ and $j = 0.825$.

Mean $KMA_iX_j = 10.24$, standard deviation = ± 0.052 .

Table 1c. Cd^{II}-thioglycolate + tartarate mixed ligand system

Conc. C_A (M)	0.000	0.010	0.020	0.040	0.060	0.080	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040
C_X (M)	0.000	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.010	0.020	0.060	0.080
30°C i_d (μ A)	8.800	8.400	8.000	7.100	7.000	6.300	7.400	7.200	6.600	6.300
$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	0.586	0.600	0.621	0.636	0.646	0.652	0.618	0.624	0.640	0.642
KMA_iX_j	-	5.892	6.020	5.978	5.970	5.970	5.954	5.391	5.970	5.932

Mean slope of log plots = 0.031, coordination numbers $i = 2.087$ and $j = 0.977$.

Mean $KMA_iX_j = 5.889$, standard deviation = ± 0.193 .

Table 1d. Pb^{II}-thioglycolate + tartarate mixed ligand system

Conc. C_A (M)	0.000	0.010	0.020	0.040	0.060	0.080	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040
C_X (M)	0.000	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.010	0.020	0.060	0.080
30°C i_d (μ A)	7.100	6.850	6.700	6.350	6.150	4.450	6.600	6.450	6.200	4.900
$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	0.404	0.454	0.466	0.486	0.495	0.502	0.468	0.478	0.493	0.495
KMA_iX_j	-	7.090	6.927	7.002	6.988	7.110	6.995	7.032	7.029	7.140

Mean slope of log plots = 0.028, coordination numbers $i = 2.023$ and $j = 1.162$.

Mean $KMA_iX_j = 7.035$, standard deviation = ± 0.067 .

Experimental

Thioglycolic, oxalic and tartaric acids (SD Fine Chemicals Ltd., India) as their sodium salts were used as complexing agents. All other reagents used were also of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade. Freshly prepared solution of thioglycolic acid in 75% methanol was used and other stock solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air-free conductivity-water. Triton X-100 (0.001%) was used as maximum suppressor and KNO_3 ($\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$) as supporting electrolyte. An auto recording Polarograph (1632, Systronics, India) with strip chart recorder (1501, Systronics, India) was used for recording current-voltage curves. The capillary characteristics in KNO_3 ($\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$) at $E_{d,e} = -0.7 \text{ V}$ in conjunction with respect to SCE were $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.436 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ ($h = 45 \text{ cm}$). Dissolved air was removed by bubbling nitrogen through the cell and the necessary corrections for

the iR drop and charging current were made as usual.

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